

NON-GEODESIC WINDING PATH EQUATIONS ON A NON AXISYMMETRIC SURFACE

G. Di Vita

Centro Italiano Ricerche Aerospaziali, Capua (CE), Italy

M. Marchetti and P. Perugini

Dipartimento Aerospaziale, Università "La Sapienza", Roma, Italy

ABSTRACT

A correct design of complex shape filament wound structures has to take into account the technological constraint of non-slippage of the fibers during their lay-down on the mandrel. Particularly, great difficulty is found for complex structures having unsymmetric shape.

The aim of this paper is to describe a mathematical model for generation and analysis of winding patterns on non-axisymmetric structures.

KEYWORDS: Filament-Wound; Non-geodesic; Simulation; Trajectories optimization; Slippage tendency.

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, there are sophisticated numerically-controlled filament winding machines that offer several independent axes of motion. They could allow the fabrication of complex shape structures in the aerospace field at a very low manufacturing cost, but developing patterns for programming such machines is still commonly achieved by a trial and error method, using full-size mandrels and toolings. This is very expensive in terms of time, material and facilities. Moreover, this method is not suitable for predicting the performance properties of the resulting part or for optimizing the manufacturing process [1,2,3,4,5]. In order to achieve this goal a mathematical model was developed. It permits to make a prediction on the stability of the roving during winding.

2. THE WINDING STABILITY CONDITION

We first analyzed the forces acting on an element of the filament (Fig. 1).

Owing to the winding tension \vec{T} a force \vec{F}_n , normal to the mandrel surface, and a

force \vec{F}_b , tangential to the mandrel surface, arise:

$$\vec{F}_n = Tc \cos \psi \vec{n}_S \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{F}_b = -Tc \sin \psi \vec{b}_S \quad (2)$$

We defined "slippage tendency" k as the ratio between the lateral and the normal force:

$$|k| = \frac{|\vec{F}_b|}{|\vec{F}_n|} = |\tan \psi| \quad (3)$$

While the normal force is balanced by the reaction of the mandrel, the lateral force have to be balanced by the friction force.

Considering a Coulomb friction force \vec{F}_f , we have:

$$|\vec{F}_f| = |\vec{F}_n| \mu_s \quad (4)$$

Therefore the stability condition

$$|\vec{F}_b| \leq |\vec{F}_f| \quad (5)$$

can be written as:

$$|k| \leq \mu_s \quad (6)$$

For more general models of friction force, where μ_s depends also on the winding tension, the winding speed and the local curvature of the mandrel, the stability condition can formally remain unchanged:

$$|k| \leq \mu_s(\vec{T}, \Omega, c, \dots) \quad (7)$$

However, an accurate experimental activity [10] evidenced a very little dependance of the friction coefficient from the mentioned parameters.

3. THE GENERALIZED SLIPPAGE TENDENCY EQUATION

From the preceding analysys the slippage tendency arises as the fundamental parameter expressing the stability of the winding path Γ . It can be related to the winding angle α , to the cylindrical coordinates r, z, ϑ of the surface of the mandrel and to its main differential properties.

Given the parametric equations of the surface S :

$$\begin{aligned} x &= r(z, \vartheta) \cos \vartheta \\ y &= r(z, \vartheta) \sin \vartheta \\ z &= z \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

and the parametric equation of the line Γ :

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x[z, \vartheta(z)] = a(z) \\ y &= y[z, \vartheta(z)] = b(z) \\ z &= z = c(z) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

the slippage tendency k has to be computed by calculating the tangent of the angle between the normal to S and the main normal to Γ (Fig. 2).

The equation of the line normal to S at $P_0(x_0, y_0, z_0)$ is:

$$\frac{x - x_0}{L_0} = \frac{y - y_0}{M_0} = \frac{z - z_0}{N_0} \quad (10)$$

where L_0 , M_0 and N_0 indicate the following determinants:

$$\begin{aligned} L &= \begin{vmatrix} y_z & z_z \\ y_\vartheta & z_\vartheta \end{vmatrix} = -r_\vartheta \sin \vartheta - r \cos \vartheta \\ M &= - \begin{vmatrix} x_z & z_z \\ x_\vartheta & z_\vartheta \end{vmatrix} = r_\vartheta \cos \vartheta - r \sin \vartheta \\ N &= \begin{vmatrix} x_z & y_z \\ x_\vartheta & y_\vartheta \end{vmatrix} = r r_z \end{aligned}$$

Defining:

$$B = L^2 + M^2 + N^2 = r_\vartheta^2 + r^2(1 + r_z^2)$$

the components of the unit vector \vec{n}_S result:

$$\begin{aligned} (\vec{n}_S)_x &= \frac{L}{\sqrt{B}} \\ (\vec{n}_S)_y &= \frac{M}{\sqrt{B}} \\ (\vec{n}_S)_z &= \frac{N}{\sqrt{B}} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The tangent to Γ at $P_0(x_0, y_0, z_0)$ is given by:

$$\frac{x - x_0}{a'(z_0)} = \frac{y - y_0}{b'(z_0)} = \frac{z - z_0}{c'(z_0)} \quad (12)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} a'(z_0) &= x_z[z, \vartheta(z)]z_z + x_\vartheta[z, \vartheta(z)]\vartheta_z(z) = r_z \cos \vartheta + (r_\vartheta \cos \vartheta - r \sin \vartheta) \\ b'(z_0) &= y_z[z, \vartheta(z)]z_z + y_\vartheta[z, \vartheta(z)]\vartheta_z(z) = r_z \sin \vartheta + (r_\vartheta \sin \vartheta + r \cos \vartheta) \\ c'(z_0) &= z_z[z, \vartheta(z)]z_z + z_\vartheta[z, \vartheta(z)]\vartheta_z(z) = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Defining:

$$A = (a')^2 + (b')^2 + (c')^2 = r_z^2 + r_\vartheta^2 \vartheta_z^2 + r^2 \vartheta_z^2 + 2r_\vartheta r_z \vartheta_z + 1$$

the components of the unit vector \vec{t} , tangent to Γ , are:

$$\begin{aligned} (\vec{t})_x &= \frac{a'}{\sqrt{A}} \\ (\vec{t})_y &= \frac{b'}{\sqrt{A}} \\ (\vec{t})_z &= \frac{c'}{\sqrt{A}} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Differentiating with respect to z the direct product $\vec{t} \cdot \vec{t}$ it is easy to demonstrate that $\frac{d\vec{t}}{dz}$ is orthogonal to \vec{t} , and thus parallel to the main normal \vec{n} to Γ .

Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d\vec{t}}{dz} \right)_z &= a'' A^{-1/2} - \frac{A^{-3/2}}{2} A' a' \\ \left(\frac{d\vec{t}}{dz} \right)_y &= b'' A^{-1/2} - \frac{A^{-3/2}}{2} A' b' \\ \left(\frac{d\vec{t}}{dz} \right)_x &= c'' A^{-1/2} - \frac{A^{-3/2}}{2} A' c' \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where:

$$A' = 2a'a'' + 2b'b'' + 2c'c''$$

Now it is possible to calculate the angle ψ from the definition of direct product:

$$\cos \psi = \frac{(\vec{n}_S)_x (d\vec{t}/dz)_x + (\vec{n}_S)_y (d\vec{t}/dz)_y + (\vec{n}_S)_z (d\vec{t}/dz)_z}{|\vec{n}_S| |(d\vec{t}/dz)|} \quad (16)$$

After some transformations we get:

$$\cos^2 \psi = \frac{A}{B} \frac{(a''L + b''M)^2}{(a'b'' - b'a'')^2 + b''^2 + a''^2}$$

and subsequently:

$$\tan \psi = \frac{\sqrt{B[(a'b'' - b'a'')^2 + b''^2 + a''^2] - A(a''L + b''M)^2}}{\sqrt{A}(a''L + b''M)}$$

Finally, the equation giving the slippage tendency is [9]:

$$\tan \psi = \frac{P_1 \alpha_x \cos \alpha + P_2 \sin^3 \alpha + P_3 \sin^2 \alpha \cos \alpha + P_4 \sin \alpha \cos^2 \alpha + P_5 \cos^3 \alpha}{(Q_1 \sin^2 \alpha + Q_2 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha + Q_3 \cos^2 \alpha) \sqrt{Q_1 + Q_4 \sin \alpha \cos \alpha}} \quad (17)$$

where the coefficients P and Q are complicated functions of the differential properties of the surface [9]:

$$P_1 = P_1(r, r_x, r_\theta)$$

$$P_2 = P_2(r, r_x, r_\theta)$$

$$P_3 = P_3(r, r_x, r_\theta, r_{x\theta})$$

$$P_4 = P_4(r, r_x, r_\theta, r_{x\theta}, r_{xx})$$

$$P_5 = P_5(r_x, r_{xx})$$

$$Q_1 = Q_1(r_x)$$

$$Q_2 = Q_2(r, r_x, r_\theta, r_{x\theta})$$

$$Q_3 = Q_3(r, r_{xx})$$

$$Q_4 = Q_4(r, r_x, r_\theta)$$

It is of great interest to note that, if S is an axisymmetric surface,

$$\begin{aligned}x &= r(z) \cos \vartheta \\y &= r(z) \sin \vartheta \\z &= z\end{aligned}\tag{18}$$

as $r_\vartheta = 0$ and $r_{z\vartheta} = 0$, the P and Q coefficients can be simplified, obtaining the well known relationship [6,7]:

$$\tan \psi = -\frac{(1 + r_z^2)(r\alpha_z \cos \alpha + r_z \sin \alpha)}{rr_{zz} \cos^2 \alpha - (1 + r_z^2) \sin^2 \alpha}\tag{19}$$

In the particular case of a geodesic trajectory, that is when $\psi = 0$, the equation (19) becomes the Clairout's equation:

$$r \sin \alpha = \text{constant}\tag{20}$$

4. THE NUMERICAL SOLUTION

To evaluate the left-hand sides of (11) and (13), the expression of ϑ_z is needed, as a function of α and the geometric features of S .

By simple geometric considerations, one obtains:

$$\frac{d\vartheta}{dz} = \frac{\sqrt{1 + r_z^2}}{\sqrt{r^2 + r_z^2}} \tan \alpha\tag{21}$$

This last equation, coupled to the (17), constitutes a set of first order ordinary differential equations:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dz} = f(\alpha, r, r_z, r_{zz}, r_\vartheta, r_{z\vartheta}, k)\tag{22}$$

$$\frac{d\vartheta}{dz} = g(\alpha, r, r_z, r_\vartheta)\tag{23}$$

The set can be integrated by use of a 4th order Runge-Kutta method, keeping the integration step Δz dependent on the value of α .

5. CONCLUSIONS

A set of equations has been presented for the calculation of slippage tendency of the fiber bundles in the filament winding process.

A computer simulation code, based on the illustrated mathematical model, was developed. It is assembled on a high performances graphic workstation [9]. The output of the code can be post-processed to get a 3-D graphic visualization [7]. Some relevant results are shown in Fig. 3 and 4.

Linking the simulation module to already existing codes [7] for thickness prediction, structural analysis and machine control, we obtain a complete CAD/CAM system for filament winding of general shape non-axisymmetric composite structures.

NOTATIONS

Γ	curve represented by the filament
S	surface of the mandrel
P	running point on Γ and S
z, r, ϑ	cylindrical coordinates of P
r_z	derivative of r with respect to z
r_{zz}	second derivative of r with respect to z
r_ϑ	derivative of r with respect to ϑ
$r_{z\vartheta}$	mixed derivative of r
α	winding angle
R	curvature radius of Γ at P
$c = 1/R$	curvature of Γ at P
μ_s	static friction coefficient
ψ	slippage angle
$k = \tan \psi$	slippage tendency
Ω	winding speed
\vec{t}	unit vector of the positive semi-tangent of Γ at P
\vec{n}	unit vector of the main positive semi-norm of Γ at P
\vec{n}_S	unit vector of the internal semi-norm to S at P
\vec{b}	$\vec{t} \times \vec{n}$
\vec{b}_S	$\vec{t} \times \vec{n}_S$
\vec{T}	winding tension
\vec{F}	force acting on the mandrel, due to the winding tension
\vec{F}_n	normal component of \vec{F}
\vec{F}_b	tangential component of \vec{F}
\vec{F}_f	friction force

REFERENCES

1. G.C. Eckold, D.G. Lloyd-Thomas, G.M. Wells, "Computer aided filament winding", C387/014, pp.127-136, United Kingdom Energy Authority, Harwell, Oxfordshire, UK.
2. J.C. Vogt, D.L. Taylor, "A workstation for off-line filament winding pattern generation", Book 2, pp.1538-1543, Proceedings of the 34th International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Reno, Nevada, U.S., 1989.
3. G.M. Wells, K.F. Mc Anulty, "Computer Aided Filament Winding Using Non-Geodesic Trajectories", in ICCM-VI, pp.1.161-1.173, Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Composite Materials, London, UK, 1987.
4. M. Marchetti, D. Cutolo, G. Di Vita, "Filament Winding of Composite Structures: Validation of the Manufacturing Process", in ICCM-VII, Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Composite Materials, Guangzhou, China, 1989.
5. Xian-li Li, Dao-hai Lin, "Non Geodesic Winding Equations on a General Surface of Revolution", in ICCM-VI, pp.1.152-1.160, Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Composite Materials, London, UK, 1987.
6. J.P. Denost, "Design of Filament-Wound Rocket Cases", in AGARD-LS-No.150, pp.5.1-5.21, Neuilly sur Seine, France, 1988.
7. G. Di Vita, M. Farioli, M. Marchetti, "Process Simulation in Filament Winding of Composite Structures", in "Composite Materials Design and Analysis", pp.19-37, Computational Mechanics Publications, Springer-Verlag, 1990.
8. M. Marchetti, D. Cutolo, G. Di Vita, "Design of domes by use of the Filament Winding technique", in ECCM-III, pp.401-408, Proceedings of the 3rd European Conference on Composite Materials, Bordeaux, France, 1989.
9. P. Perugini, Antropometrico, "Application and extension of the filament winding process to general shape structures", M.Sc. Thesis in Aeronautical Engineering (in italian), Università "La Sapienza", Roma, 1990.
10. G. Di Vita, M. Grimaldi, M. Marchetti, P. Moroni, "The filament winding manufacturing technique: Studies on the determination of the friction coefficient and on the optimization of the feed-eye motion", pp.972-979, Proceedings of the 22nd International SAMPE Technical Conference, Boston, USA, 1990.

FIGURE 1. Scheme of the forces acting on a cross-section of the tow

FIGURE 2. Geometry of a non-geodesic winding path

FIGURE 3. Particular of a winding simulation on a non-axisymmetric mandrel

FIGURE 4. Simulation of the filament winding process on a typical non-axisymmetric aeronautical structure

